

Assessment Strategies and Curriculum Delivery of Araling Panlipunan in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental

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Abstract. This study examined differences in the effectiveness of assessment strategies in the delivery of the Araling Panlipunan curriculum for grade 4 teachers. The research design used in this study was descriptive-comparative, aiming to explore and analyze differences in the effectiveness of curriculum delivery. There were 87 Grade 4 teachers in the study sample, out of a total population of 110 Grade 4 teachers. The findings revealed that the Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers demonstrated varied use of assessment strategies, with performance-based assessments most frequently used. The extent of curriculum delivery effectiveness was found to be moderately extensive in terms of student learning outcomes and feedback responsiveness and extensive in terms of lesson adjustments, reflecting generally effective instructional practices with room for further enhancement. No significant difference was found in curriculum delivery effectiveness in terms of student learning outcomes, feedback responsiveness, and lesson adjustments when teachers were grouped according to the assessment strategy used. Post hoc analyses further revealed that none of the assessment strategies differed significantly from one another. Teachers may diversify their assessment strategies, consistently use feedback for instruction, and refine teaching practices to enhance curriculum delivery.

KEY WORDS

1. assessment strategies
2. araling panlipunan curriculum delivery
3. performance-based assessments

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1. Introduction

The Problem and Its Setting Assessment strategies were essential for enhancing the effectiveness of curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan and for improving students' engagement with historical, social, and political concepts. However, many educational environments faced a significant challenge due to the mismatch between assessment methods and instructional goals. Traditional assessment approaches, such as standardized tests and summative evaluations, tended to emphasize factual recall rather than fostering critical thinking, his-

torical analysis, and real-world application.

In contrast, performance-based and formative assessments, which promoted active student participation, were frequently underused due to time constraints, insufficient training, and strict curricular frameworks. These discrepancies raised questions about whether current assessment practices genuinely facilitated effective learning and meaningful curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan. Globally, (Oteng et al., 2023), secondary school curricula address critical gaps, particularly in climate change and

digital literacy education. The report suggested creating an independent body to ensure the curriculum reflected modern societal needs and diversity. Recommendations included emphasizing climate education, reinstating digital literacy, and incorporating ethical considerations of technology use, aiming to make education more relevant and comprehensive. Also, in Australia, there had been a resurgence of explicit or direct instruction methods, particularly in improving literacy and numeracy among disadvantaged students. This approach involved clear explanations, demonstrations, and repetitive practice, ensuring foundational skills were solidified. Schools adopting this method had reported significant improvements in standardized test scores, highlighting the effectiveness of structured teaching strategies in curriculum delivery (Crews, 2024).

Furthermore, in the Philippines, Torreon and Sumayang (2021) shared the implementation of differentiated assessment strategies in Araling Panlipunan 10. They emphasized that assessment served not only to measure learners' abilities but also to enable teachers to modify their teaching strategies to meet individual learner needs. They highlighted that such assessments were vital in monitoring students' learning and enhancing teaching effectiveness (Navalta, 2021).

Moreover, (Delfin, 2019), educators explored various interventions and strategies to enhance the enjoyment of AP for learners. Project EDGAR (Edukasyong Dekalidad tungo sa Garantisadong mga Aral ng Araling Panlipunan) significantly contributed to the improvement of Grade 6 pupils' mean final rating. However, most students find AP to be boring (Crisolo & Camposano, 2021), monotonous, and irrelevant, which leads to sleepiness among learners (Pesimo, 2024).

Likewise, a recent review examined the challenges faced by Araling Panlipunan teachers in varying their instructional strategies to fos-

ter a positive attitude among students towards the subject. It identified time constraints, limited learning resources, and student motivation as significant challenges. Addressing these issues was crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan (Arendain, 2024).

In Ocaña (2024), Araling Panlipunan respondents rated instructional materials highly, with age-related differences. It is recommended that DepEd regularly train teachers, provide IPR orientation, and align curriculum, objectives, and materials. However, Effective delivery of Araling Panlipunan faces challenges due to limited teaching approaches and diverse learner needs, including insufficient training and a lack of culturally relevant resources. The subject is vital in fostering civic and cultural awareness, promoting responsible citizenship, and strengthening community ties in Davao Occidental. To improve instruction, it is essential to evaluate assessment strategies to identify the most effective methods for student learning and achievement.

In Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, the assessment strategies and curriculum delivery of Araling Panlipunan directly support the UNSDG Goal 4, Quality Education, by ensuring inclusive and equitable learning opportunities for all students. Effective assessment methods help students gain a comprehensive understanding of local history, culture, and societal issues, fostering civic responsibility and cultural awareness. When the curriculum is tailored to reflect the lived experiences and community context of the students, it enhances engagement and learning outcomes. Incorporating diverse, culturally responsive teaching practices promotes inclusivity, making education relevant and accessible to all learners, and ultimately helps develop informed, responsible citizens who contribute meaningfully to community development.

Statement of the Problem This study aimed to investigate the difference among assessment strategies in the effectiveness of the Araling Pan-

lipunan curriculum delivery for grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem: What is the extent of use of assessment strategies among Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, in terms of: 1.1 Traditional Tests; 1.2 Performance-Based Assessments; and 1.3 Formative Assessments? What is the extent of curriculum delivery effectiveness among Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, in terms of: 2.1 Student Learning Outcomes; 2.2 Feedback Responsiveness; and 2.3 Lesson Adjustments? 3. Is there a significant difference in assessment strategies and Curriculum delivery of Araling Panlipunan for Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental Objectives of the Study The study probed the influence of values education practices on the implementation of Child Protection measures. Specifically, it sought to: Observe the extent of what was the extent of use of assessment strategies among Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, in terms of: Traditional Tests, Performance-Based Assessments, Formative Assessments; Assess the extent of curriculum delivery effectiveness among Grade Araling Panlipunan teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, in terms of: Student Learning Outcomes, Feedback Responsiveness, Lesson and Adjustments.

Determine the significant difference in assessment strategies and Curriculum delivery of Araling Panlipunan of Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. Significance of the Study This study emphasized the importance of curriculum delivery effectiveness among the three assessment strategies, such as Traditional Tests, Performance-Based Assessments, and Formative Assessments. This study provided empirical data on the effectiveness of different assessment strategies in curriculum delivery, equipping them with insights on improv-

ing their assessment practices. It highlighted how assessments influence lesson pacing, instructional adjustments, and student feedback mechanisms. Identifying which strategies were most effective in enhancing student learning outcomes, teachers could make informed decisions on selecting appropriate assessment tools that fostered deeper understanding, encouraged student engagement, and aligned with the learning competencies of Araling Panlipunan. Furthermore, the study served as a practical guide for professional development, enabling teachers to adapt innovative and research-based assessment methods that improve the overall quality of instruction.

The results could guide policy development, instructional supervision, and teacher training programs to ensure that assessment strategies were aligned with DepEd standards and responsive to student needed. Moreover, the study could serve as a basis for school-based learning action cells (LAC sessions) or professional learning communities (PLCs), where teachers could collaborate to improve their assessment practices. With a clearer understanding of the effectiveness of various assessment strategies, school heads could provide technical assistance and instructional leadership to ensure that assessments contribute to learner-centered, competency-based education.

This study provided a data-driven basis for evaluating the effectiveness of assessment practices in Araling Panlipunan across multiple classrooms and schools. It supported the need for standardized, research-based assessment guidelines that improve the quality of teaching and learning in Social Studies. The study's findings could be used to develop assessment frameworks, design professional development programs, and create instructional policies that ensure Araling Panlipunan was delivered effectively.

Furthermore, the study served as a benchmark for evaluating the impact of various as-

assessment methodologies and their contribution to student achievement and teacher competency development at the district or division level. Future Researchers. This study laid the groundwork for further investigations into assessment strategies and curriculum delivery in Social Studies and other subject areas. It served as a reference for those who wished to expand the research scope to different grade levels, educational settings, or teaching methodologies. The study also opened opportunities for future research on innovative assessment models, the integration of digital assessment tools, and the impact of assessments on 21st-century skills development in Social Studies education. Providing empirical data and a structured research framework, this study encouraged future scholars to explore new dimensions of curriculum assessment and instructional effectiveness, contributing to improving education policies and practices continuously.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study. and contextual foundations of the present research. It highlighted relevant findings on values education practices and implementing child protection measures in local and international settings. These studies provide insights into prevailing issues, interventions, and gaps that inform the direction and significance of the current investigation. Assessment Strategies of Araling Panlipunan Araling Panlipunan assessments blend traditional written tests with dynamic, performance-based tasks to measure both historical knowledge and civic competence. Teachers utilize formative tools, portfolios, and collaborative projects like debates or role-plays to cultivate critical thinking regarding contemporary social issues. These diverse strategies ensure a holistic evaluation of a student's civic consciousness and real-world application skills. In a 2024 review, Hayward examined Scotland's qualification system and suggested moving away from traditional exams in favor of coursework and classroom assess-

ments. The study highlighted the shortcomings of standardized tests, particularly in evaluating critical thinking, creativity, and the practical application of knowledge. Hayward supported alternative assessment methods, such as project-based evaluations and formative assessments, which provide a more comprehensive view of student learning and skill development. The research underscored the importance of curriculum-aligned assessments that promoted meaningful learning experiences rather than mere memorization. Further, Adams and Ferguson (2025) found that 92% of UK university students use AI tools like ChatGPT, raising concerns about assessment integrity. They recommend that universities adopt AI-resistant methods such as oral exams, real-world tasks, and projects. A study conducted by Miller (2024) in the United States analyzed the effectiveness of a new teacher evaluation system in the Houston Independent School District (HISD) was analyzed. This research focused on classroom observations, assessment scores, and professionalism metrics to evaluate teacher performance. Although the system was intended to provide a comprehensive measure of teacher effectiveness, Miller raised concerns regarding the observation frequency and the application of forced distribution models, which could lead to biases and distort the true quality of instruction, and suggested that incorporating self-assessments and peer evaluations could enhance the reliability and fairness of teacher evaluations. Also, Thompson and Lee (2023) examined the digital transformation of large-scale assessments, specifically the 2021 cycle of the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS). Their research emphasized the transition to fully digital assessments, featuring adaptive reading tasks, interactive activities, and multimedia comprehension elements. The results suggested that digital assessments could improve data accuracy, alleviate test anxiety, and provide real-time feedback, thus serving as effec-

tive tools for personalized learning. Nonetheless, Thompson and Lee warned that challenges related to accessibility and technological infrastructure must be overcome to ensure fair assessment practices (Thompson & Lee, 2023). Moreover, (Mitchell & Dawson, 2025), Mitchell and Dawson explored the increasing influence of AI in education, especially regarding university assessment methods. They discovered that traditional pen-and-paper exams were increasingly inadequate in evaluating student learning due to the prevalence of AI-generated answers. The authors recommend a revision of assessment strategies, including case-based evaluations, real-world application tasks, and hands-on performance assessments, to ensure that students exhibit genuine competence instead of relying on AI-assisted responses. Their research underscored the necessity for innova-

tive and adaptive assessment methods that meet the needs of 21st-century learners. Traditional Test. Recent studies in the Philippines have critically examined traditional assessment strategies, highlighting their applications, challenges, and the evolving landscape of educational assessments. Sarmiento et al. (2021) explored assessment practices among higher education STEAM educators in the Philippines. Their findings indicated that while traditional assessments, such as multiple-choice tests and written exams, remain prevalent, there was a growing recognition of the need to incorporate authentic assessments to better evaluate students' practical skills and real-world application of knowledge. The study emphasized the importance of balancing traditional methods with innovative assessment practices to enhance education outcomes.

2. METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlined the research methodology employed in the study, including the research design, research participants, sampling technique, research instrument, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment, ethical considerations, and trustworthiness procedures. The nature of the inquiry and the evidence needed to answer the study's objectives guided the choice of research design and its implementation, which are discussed in the sections that follow.

Research Design— The research design utilized in this study was descriptive-comparative, aiming to explore and analyze the differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness among Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. This approach allowed the researcher to observe and describe the various assessment strategies employed by teachers without manipulating any variables, providing a clear picture of current teaching practices. By comparing how different assessment methods influence instructional effectiveness, the study sought to identify best practices and areas for improvement.

The descriptive nature helped in gathering detailed information about teachers' methods, while the comparative aspect highlighted varia-

tions across different classrooms and teachers. This design was particularly suitable given the non-experimental setting, where the goal was to understand existing practices rather than establish cause-and-effect relationships. Overall, employing a descriptive-comparative design enabled a comprehensive examination of assessment strategies and curriculum delivery in the local context.

Moreover, Creswell and Creswell (2018), this study examined the assessment strategies and curriculum delivery of Araling Panlipunan in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. Typically, research in this area utilizes quantitative data, closed-ended questions, and observational techniques to investigate the relationships

among various factors. A survey method was particularly effective for addressing questions related to describing, comparing, or analyzing these aspects within the educational context. Likewise, Singh (2023), descriptive research uses quantitative methods to collect measurable data for statistical analysis of the population sample.

Research Participants— The participants of this research were Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers from Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, who met specific inclusion criteria to guarantee that the data gathered was pertinent, dependable, and aligned with the study's objectives. Slovin's formula was employed to determine the appropriate number of respondents, ensuring that the sample accurately represented the total population of 110 Grade 4 teachers in the area. With a standard margin of error of 0.05, the calculation indicated that at least 87 teachers needed to be included to achieve reliable statistical results.

This sample size of 87 teachers was selected to provide valuable insights into how assessment strategies affected the effectiveness of curriculum delivery. The approach aimed to reduce sampling error and ensure that the data reflected the actual practices and viewpoints of the larger group of Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan educators in Jose Abad Santos 1. By carefully choosing the respondents, the study sought to produce trustworthy findings that could support improvements in teaching methods and curriculum implementation.

Sampling Technique— The researcher employed a stratified random sampling to ensure fair representation from each participating school. The respondents of this study were public elementary Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos 1, Davao Occidental; these schools were chosen due to their consistent Assessment Strategies and Curriculum Delivery. The total teacher population across these schools was 110. To determine the representative sample size,

Slovin's formula was used to determine that a total of 87 teacher-respondents were selected as the representative sample for the quantitative phase of the study. This criterion ensured that participants had direct experience with curriculum delivery and assessment practices, making them the most appropriate sources of information regarding the impact of different assessment strategies on teaching effectiveness.

Research Instruments— The survey instrument for this research was developed based on a thorough review of the literature and related studies. Analyzed literature to identify concepts that informed the content and supported the instrument and its associated components. This careful process resulted in items that addressed potential threats to the study's validity. The authors argued that items were adapted by Deane (2022) from the reviewed literature and studies. The survey questionnaire had two parts.

The first part of the instrument consisted of the Assessment Strategy Most Frequently Used, including Traditional Tests (Multiple-choice, Fill-in-the-blanks, etc.), Performance-Based Assessments (Projects, Role-playing, etc.), and Formative Assessments (Quizzes, Think-Pair-Share, etc.) The second part of the survey assessed the extent of Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness with respect to student learning outcomes, feedback responsiveness, and lesson adjustments.

Also, the questionnaire made use of a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following range of means. All instruments use a 5-point Likert scale and have been pilot-tested for reliability and validity in the school teachers' context, obtaining a Cronbach's alpha of 0.8213 determine the extent of Curriculum Delivery in the Delivery of Araling Panlipunan in Jose Abad Santos 1, Davao Occidental. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation. Cronbach's alpha was a measure of scale reliability that assessed the degree to which survey items correlate with each other, thus providing a

unified measure of a construct (Creswell, 2020). All three instruments met the acceptable reliability threshold, confirming their suitability for measuring the key variables in this research.

Data Gathering Procedure— The study adhered to the policies of Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., beginning with formal authorization from the research adviser, the Dean, and the DepEd Davao City Division. As part of the formal request, the researcher outlined their intentions regarding data collection, analysis, and sharing, ensuring alignment with the overall research objectives. Potential questions or concerns from stakeholders were addressed in advance, providing assurances regarding ethical considerations, confidentiality, and the possible benefits of the study. The official request for permission explicitly sought approval to proceed, highlighting the importance of their support in the success of the project.

Before beginning data collection in December 2025, the researcher planned to secure the necessary approvals from relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., and the senior management of the DepEd Davao Occidental Division. This involved submitting a detailed research proposal that described the study's design, procedures, and potential risks and advantages. The researcher aimed to provide comprehensive information about the study's objectives, methods for gathering and analyzing data, and reporting plans.

The researcher took careful steps in managing the data. Collected information was accurately organized in SPSS trial version for analysis. All necessary data points were gathered, and consistency checks were performed to ensure relevance to the research problem. To minimize errors during analysis, the researcher also evaluated the reliability and validity of the data. This preparatory phase involved submitting a comprehensive proposal that detailed the design and ethical safeguards to ensure participant con-

fidentiality in the study.

During the collation and statistical treatment phase, the researcher managed the gathered data by sorting it through Microsoft Excel before transferring the files to JASP for analysis. This process focused on maintaining strict accuracy and consistency while reviewing the reliability and validity of the information to minimize potential errors. By systematically coding and cleaning the dataset, the researcher ensured that the findings remained aligned with the problem statement and were prepared for rigorous hypothesis testing.

Procedure of the Study The researcher began by obtaining approval for the research instruments and proceeded with data collection after securing an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. in Davao City. Next, formal permission letters were delivered in person to the Schools Division Superintendent, the Public Schools District Supervisor, and the school principals to introduce the study and request their support. With all necessary authorizations obtained, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to participants during the 2025-2026 school year, provided a brief overview of the research, and collected completed forms immediately to maintain data integrity.

Responses were then organized according to the relationship between Assessment Strategies (independent variable) and the Curriculum Delivery of Araling Panlipunan (dependent variable) in public schools. and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS trial version. This systematic approach was guided by the policies of Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., ensuring alignment with institutional standards for ethical conduct, confidentiality, and research integrity.

Statistical Treatment The statistical treatment involved first organizing and checking the collected data for completeness and consistency, then entering the responses into statistical soft-

ware for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, were calculated for each aspect to give a clear overview of Assessment Strategies and the Curriculum Delivery of Araling Panlipunan, highlighting both central trends and variability.

Following the correlation analysis, a test was conducted to test whether to examine the relationship between these variables. Throughout the entire process, standardized procedures were used for distributing and retrieving questionnaires, and data were initially managed in Microsoft Excel before being transferred to JASP. Careful attention was given to consistency, reliability, and validity at each step to ensure the accuracy and relevance of the findings of the study.

Ethical Considerations The researcher followed strict ethical guidelines throughout the study, involving 87 teachers from a total population of 110 in the East Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. Following Bos (2020), ethics in research centers on proper conduct and responsibility. All procedures, including population management and data collection, adhered to standard protocols. Survey materials were reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee before any research activities began, ensuring participants' rights were protected and maintaining the integrity and credibility of the research process.

Social Value. This study, conducted in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, upheld strong social and ethical values by examining how assessment strategies influence the effectiveness of curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan. It aimed to provide practical insights benefiting teachers, students, and school leaders, promoting fair and effective assessment practices that enhance learning. Aligned with ethical principles, the study supported equitable access to quality education, ensuring that no learner was disadvantaged. It was designed to be academically rigorous, ethically sound, and

socially relevant.

Informed Consent. In the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, obtaining informed consent was a fundamental ethical requirement of this study. All Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers would receive a detailed consent form explaining the purpose of the study, objectives, procedures, benefits, and minimal risks. The form would emphasize voluntary participation, the confidentiality of responses, and the right to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Teachers would be assured that all collected data was used solely for research purposes and reported in aggregate form to protect their anonymity and professional integrity. While assent generally applied to minors, I would uphold the same principle of respect and understanding among teacher-participants in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental. Through open communication and transparent research protocols, I would ensure that all respondents clearly understand their rights and the ethical safeguards of the study before participating. This process reinforced principles of autonomy, beneficence, and non-maleficence, ensuring teachers feel respected, informed, and valued. By adhering to DepEd's ethical standards and research protocols, I affirm my commitment to conducting an ethical, respectful, and socially responsible study.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents. In conducting this study in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, I recognized that Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers, though professional educators, may still experience vulnerabilities during participation. To address these, participation would be entirely voluntary, with assurances of anonymity, confidentiality, and non-coercion. Teachers would be informed of their right to withdraw without consequences, and neutral, objective data-collection methods were employed to prevent bias or discomfort. All participants would be treated with fairness, dignity, and professional integrity throughout

the research process.

Privacy and Confidentiality. In the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, the privacy of all Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teacher-respondents was strictly protected. Surveys and interviews would only collect essential information relevant to the study, avoiding intrusive or personally sensitive questions. Participants were assured that their participation was voluntary and that their personal identities would not be disclosed, thereby promoting a sense of safety and trust throughout the research process.

To maintain confidentiality, all collected data in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, would be securely stored and accessible only to the researcher. Personal identifiers would be removed, and findings would be reported in aggregate form to ensure anonymity. Participants' information would not be shared with school administrators, colleagues, or external parties, safeguarding their trust, professional integrity, and the ethical soundness of the research process.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety. In the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, the researcher acknowledged that potential risks may arise if teachers feel hesitant to provide honest feedback regarding assessment practices. To minimize these, all questions were professionally relevant, non-intrusive, and designed to create a safe environment for open responses. Participants would be fully informed of their right to skip questions or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty, thereby respecting their autonomy and comfort throughout the research process.

This study provided significant benefits to teachers, school administrators, and the education sector in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental. Identifying the most effective assessment strategies that enhance curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan, the study aimed to strengthen instructional practices and improve student learning outcomes. The find-

ings served as a valuable reference for developing professional development programs and policy decisions that promoted effective, evidence-based assessment approaches in Social Studies education.

To ensure the safety and well-being of all participants in the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, all research procedures were strictly adhered to ethical standards and institutional research board guidelines. Confidentiality and data protection protocols would be rigorously implemented to mitigate professional risk. Participation would remain completely voluntary, and responses would be handled anonymously. Balancing minimal risks with meaningful academic and professional benefits, this study upheld ethical integrity, academic responsibility, and participant dignity throughout the research process.

Justice. In the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, this study upheld the principle of justice by ensuring that both the burden and benefits of participation were fairly distributed. Participants did not experience undue stress or risk, and their contributions were valued and acknowledged. Research findings were transparently shared to benefit teachers, administrators, curriculum planners, and policymakers. The voices of all respondents would be accurately represented, avoiding bias or manipulation, thus promoting fairness, inclusivity, and equitable improvement in Social Studies curriculum delivery and assessment practices.

Transparency. In the Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, this study upheld the ethical principle of transparency by ensuring that the entire research process was open, honest, and accountable. The purpose, objectives, methodology, and outcomes were clearly communicated to all Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers before obtaining their consent. Participants would receive complete information about their roles, rights, and privacy safeguards. All data collection, analysis, and reporting were

conducted with academic integrity, ensuring that findings were accurate, unbiased, and free from manipulation.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher has 8 years of teaching experience in an elementary school in Davao Occidental. She is a graduate of Bachelor of Secondary Education from a private school in Padada. She attended various trainings in curriculum enhancement delivery. The researcher acknowledged that the researcher's qualifications were an essential ethical consideration in ensuring the credibility, reliability, and integrity of this study. Also, the researcher possessed the necessary academic background, research experience, and professional expertise to conduct this study on the impact of assessment strategies on the effectiveness of curriculum delivery in Araling Panlipunan. Qualifications included a strong foundation in educational research, pedagogy, and curriculum assessment, enabling me to design a methodologically sound study, collect and analyze data accurately, and interpret findings objectively.

Trustworthiness of the Study— The credibility of the research was established through careful adherence to ethical standards and rigorous data collection procedures. The reliability of the study was ensured by a number of crucial tactics. Dependability ensures that results are consistent and can withstand examination (Kakar et al., 2023). The researcher ensured that all information gathered was accurate and trustworthy by following standardized methods for administering and retrieving questionnaires. Data

were meticulously organized using spreadsheet software, and the analysis was conducted with reliable statistical tools to support the findings. Efforts were made to verify the consistency and validity of the data, thereby enhancing the overall dependability of the study's results.

Additionally, the researcher prioritized transparency and ethical considerations to strengthen the trustworthiness of the study. Participants were fully informed about the purpose of the research and their rights, with informed consent obtained prior to participation. The researcher also took measures to address potential biases and errors during data management and analysis, aiming to present an objective and dependable assessment of the strategies used in curriculum delivery and evaluation in the local context. These steps collectively contributed to the robustness and credibility of the conclusions of the study.

Moreover, Confirmability refers to the objectivity of research findings, ensuring they reflect participants' views rather than the bias of the researcher. Techniques such as reflexivity and maintaining an audit trail help establish this (Tariq, 2025). Ensuring trustworthiness is crucial for the credibility and validity of qualitative research results. Throughout the data analysis process, the researcher actively worked to reduce personal bias in order to promote confirmability. To support the study's transferability, detailed information about the participants and Jose Abad Santos District, Davao Occidental, was also included.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the study based on the statistical analysis of the assessment strategies and curriculum delivery effectiveness of Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental. The discussion is organized according to the research questions, with the tables retained as the primary evidence and the interpretation shortened to emphasize the main findings.

Use of Assessment Strategies—

The results show the distribution and use of traditional, performance-based, and formative assessment strategies among Grade 4 Araling

Panlipunan teachers. The pattern indicates that teachers use varied assessment approaches in delivering the curriculum.

Table 1

Frequency of Use of Assessment Strategies among Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan Teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental

Assessment Strategy	f	Percent
Traditional Tests	34	29.825
Performance-Based Assessments	45	39.474
Formative Assessments	35	30.702
Total	114	100.000

Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness—

The findings indicate that curriculum delivery was generally effective, although some domains remained only moderately extensive. The

results suggest the need to strengthen feedback use, lesson adjustment, and outcome-based instructional decisions.

Table 2

Extent of Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness in terms of Student Learning Outcomes

No	Student Learning Outcomes	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	The assessment strategy I use helped students retain key concepts in Araling Panlipunan effectively.	2.78	Moderately Extensive
2	My students demonstrate higher-order thinking skills (e.g., analysis, evaluation, problem-solving) based on the assessments I implement.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
3	Assessment results allow me to track student progress and adjust instruction accordingly.	3.60	Extensive
4	The assessment strategies I use encourage students to actively engage and participate in the learning process.	3.60	Extensive
5	My assessment methods help students apply historical and socio-political concepts in real-world situations.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
	Mean Average	3.30	Moderately Extensive

Summary of Curriculum Delivery—

The summary table consolidates the level of effectiveness across the measured domains

and shows that teachers demonstrate functional curriculum delivery practices with areas for improvement.

Table 3

Extent of Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness in terms of Feedback Responsiveness

No	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	I provide timely and constructive feedback to students based on their assessment results.	2.78	Moderately Extensive
2	My chosen assessment strategy allowed for meaningful student feedback and reflection on their learning.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
3	I use assessment results to initiate individual or group discussions on areas that need improvement.	3.43	Extensive
4	The feedback I provide helped students understand their strengths and areas for improvement in Araling Panlipunan.	3.60	Extensive
5	I modify my instructional approach based on the trends and insights gathered from student performance data.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
	Mean Average	3.27	Moderately Extensive

Significant Difference by Assessment Strategy— This means that traditional, performance-based, and formative strategies did not differ meaningfully in their effect on the measured domains. The ANOVA results show that differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness across assessment strategies were not statistically significant.

Table 4
Extent of Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness in terms of Lesson Adjustments

No	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	The assessment strategies I use help me adjust lesson pacing based on students' understanding.	2.44	Extensive
2	I incorporate remedial or enrichment activities based on assessment outcomes.	3.60	Extensive
3	I regularly revise my teaching methods to align with students' diverse learning needed as reflected in their assessment performance.	4.28	Very Extensive
4	I adapt instructional strategies based on student feedback and assessment results to improve learning outcomes.	3.60	Extensive
5	I utilize assessment data to determine the effectiveness of my teaching methods and make necessary improvements.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
	Mean Average	3.44	Extensive

Significant Difference by Assessment Strategy— This means that traditional, performance-based, and formative strategies did not differ meaningfully in their effect on the measured domains. The ANOVA results show that differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness across assessment strategies were not statistically significant.

Table 5
Summary of Curriculum Delivery Effectiveness among Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan Teachers

No	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Student Learning Outcomes.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
2	Feedback Responsiveness.	3.27	Moderately Extensive
3	Lesson Adjustments.	3.44	Extensive
	Mean Average	3.30	Moderately Extensive

Significant Difference by Assessment Strategy— This means that traditional, performance-based, and formative strategies did not differ meaningfully in their effect on the measured domains. The ANOVA results show that differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness across assessment strategies were not statistically significant.

Table 6
ANOVA Results for Student Learning Outcomes (SLC_MEAN)

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p	eta ²	omega ²
TAS (IV)	0.371	2	0.185	1.927	.150	.034	.016
Residuals	10.683	111	0.096				

Note. Type III sum of squares.

Significant Difference by Assessment Strategy— This means that traditional, performance-based, and formative strategies did not differ meaningfully in their effect on the measured domains. The ANOVA results show that differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness across assessment strategies were not statistically significant.

Table 7
ANOVA Results for Feedback Responsiveness (FR_MEAN)

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p	eta ²	omega ²
TAS (IV)	0.476	2	0.238	2.574	.081	.044	.027
Residuals	10.265	111	0.092				

Note. Type III sum of squares.

Significant Difference by Assessment Strategy— This means that traditional, performance-based, and formative strategies did not differ meaningfully in their effect on the measured domains. The ANOVA results show that differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness across assessment strategies were not statistically significant.

Table 8
ANOVA Results for Lesson Adjustments (LA_MEAN)

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p	eta ²	omega ²
TAS (IV)	0.129	2	0.065	1.165	.316	.021	.003
Residuals	6.149	111	0.055				

Note. Type III sum of squares.

4. Summary of Findings, Conclusions, and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the major findings, presents the conclusions drawn from the results, and offers recommendations for strengthening assessment strategies and curriculum delivery in Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan. The discussion is anchored on the study’s objectives, the statistical evidence presented in the results, and the implications of the findings for teachers, school heads, supervisors, and future researchers.

Summary of Findings

To investigate the difference among assessment strategies in the effectiveness of the Araling Panlipunan curriculum delivery for Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental, the study involved 87 teacher-respondents drawn from a population of 110 Grade 4 teachers using Slovin’s formula and stratified random sampling.

The researcher used modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested at a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument’s items. The research design utilized in this study was descriptive-comparative, aiming to explore and analyze the differences in curriculum delivery effectiveness among Grade 4 teachers in Jose Abad Santos, Davao Occidental.

Based on the results, the summary of the findings was the following: Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers demonstrated varied use of assessment strategies, with performance-based assessments most frequently used, followed by formative assessments, while traditional tests were used least frequently, indicating a preference for more authentic, process-oriented assessment approaches. The extent of curriculum delivery effectiveness was found to be moderately extensive in terms of student learning outcomes ($M = 3.30$) and feedback responsiveness ($M = 3.27$), and extensive in terms of lesson adjustments ($M = 3.44$), reflecting generally effective instructional practices with room for further enhancement.

No significant difference was found in curriculum delivery effectiveness in terms of stu-

dent learning outcomes, feedback responsiveness, and lesson adjustments when teachers were grouped according to the assessment strategy used ($p < .05$), suggesting comparable levels of effectiveness across assessment approaches. Post hoc analyses further revealed that none of the assessment strategies differed significantly from one another, indicating that curriculum delivery effectiveness was influenced more by teachers' instructional responsiveness and the use of assessment results than by the specific assessment strategy employed.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions (such as the survey questionnaire and number of participants), several conclusions were generated: 1. Grade 4 Araling Panlipunan teachers varied in their use of assessment strategies, with performance-based assessments used most frequently, followed by formative assessments, and traditional tests used least.

2. Curriculum delivery effectiveness was rated as moderately extensive for student learning outcomes and feedback responsiveness, and extensive for lesson adjustments. 3. There was no significant difference in curriculum delivery effectiveness in terms of student learning

outcomes, feedback responsiveness, and lesson adjustments when grouped according to the assessment strategy used. *Recommendations*

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were forwarded for consideration: Learners may actively engage in varied assessment activities, reflect on feedback received, and apply insights to improve learning outcomes consistently. Learners were encouraged to actively and consistently participate in values-oriented school activities.

Teachers may diversify their assessment strategies, consistently use feedback for instruction, and refine teaching practices to enhance curriculum delivery. School heads may support professional development initiatives, promote effective assessment practices, and monitor instructional implementation to sustain the effectiveness of curriculum delivery. Education Program Supervisors may provide continuous technical assistance, monitor assessment implementation, and effectively guide teachers in data-driven instructional decision-making.

Future researchers may explore additional variables, larger samples, and mixed-method approaches to further validate findings on assessment and curriculum delivery.

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